

Therapeutic management of classic icteric leptospirosis in an adult horse - A case report

Babul Rudra Paul¹, Dushyant Kumar Sharma¹, *Raguvaran R², Shivvaran Singh³, Jitendra Singh Gandhar⁴, U.K. De⁵

¹Ph.D. Scholar, ²Scientist, Division of Medicine, ³Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Microbiology, ⁴M.V.Sc. Scholar,

⁵Senior Scientist, R.V.P and T.V.C.C, ICAR-IVRI, Izatnagar, UP-243122

Abstract

A 3.5 year old horse was presented to Referral Veterinary Polyclinic, ICAR-IVRI with a history of lethargy and red coloured urine. Clinical examination revealed icteric mucous membranes, tachycardia and tachypnea, and a temperature of 102.5°F. A serum sample was found positive for leptospira antibodies by latex agglutination test as well as microscopic agglutination test (MAT). Serum biochemistry revealed an elevated level of indirect bilirubin with a normal level of liver specific enzymes. The horse was successfully treated with Amoxicillin and sulbactam and other symptomatic therapy.

Key words: Leptospirosis, horse, jaundice, hemoglobinuria, MAT

Leptospirosis considered as a global problem (Verma *et al.*, 2013), which has a major economic impact on livestock industries and is an important zoonotic disease (Ellis, 2015) caused by spirochetes belonging to the genus *Leptospira* (Levett, 2001). More than 12 pathogenic species of *Leptospira* are involved in infection. However, seroprevalence and isolation studies indicate that the horse is susceptible to a wide range of serovars, in particular, serovars belonging to the Pomona (serovar Kennewicki) and Grippotyphosa, but also to Icterohaemorrhagiae, Autumnalis, Sejroe, Canicola, and Ballum serogroups (Wood and Townsend 1999). Antibodies against serovar Bratislava is the most common antibodies detected in horses globally (Ellis, 2015). Virulent leptospire shedded from infected or carrier animals through the urine can persist for prolonged periods in environments and transmission to a new host usually occurs through contact with contaminated water (Vinetz, 1997; Bharti *et al.*, 2003; Adler and de la Peña Moctezuma, 2010). The majority of infections remain asymptomatic (Hathaway *et al.*, 1981), however mild form of equine leptospirosis is characterized by low-grade fever, listlessness, and anorexia. While typical signs in the severe form includes conjunctival suffusion, jaundice, anemia, petechial hemorrhages on the mucosa and general depression. Foals are mainly suffered from classic icteric leptospirosis, which is comparatively rare in adult horses (Verma *et al.*, 2013). Although clinical equine leptospirosis has been considered

relatively uncommon (Broux *et al.*, 2012) and infection in adult horses is subclinical (Verma *et al.*, 2013). The present report describes the therapeutic management of Leptospirosis in an adult horse.

Case History, Observations and Treatment

A 3.5 year old horse was presented to Referral Veterinary Polyclinic, ICAR-IVRI with complaints of lethargy, red coloured urine and bilateral swelling in the metatarso-phalangeal joint. Clinical examination revealed icteric mucous membranes (Fig.1), tachycardia and tachypnea, and a temperature of 102.5° F. Blood, serum and urine samples were collected before and after treatment for different laboratory tests. Examination of Peripheral blood smear stained with Giemsa stain found negative of any hemoprotozoa. A serum sample was found positive for leptospira antibodies by latex agglutination test (Fig. 2) as well as microscopic agglutination test (MAT) (Fig.3). Complete blood count examination showed anemia, leukocytosis with neutrophilia. Serum biochemistry revealed an elevated level of indirect bilirubin with normal level of liver specific enzymes. (Tab.1). Gradual changes in urine color from red to light yellow had been seen during the treatment period (Fig: 4). Based on history, clinical symptoms, and laboratory finding, the case was confirmed as equine leptospirosis. The horse was treated with Inj. Amoxicillin and sulbactam (Amoxirum forte) ® @ 10 mg/Kg BW IV BID, Inj. Meloxicam and paracetamol combination (Melonex Plus) ® @ 0.3 mg/Kg, IM OD, Inj. Pheneramine maleate (Avilin)® @

Table 1: Hemato-Biochemical changes in affected horse

Parameters	Before treatment	After treatment (5 days after therapy)	Reference Value
Hemoglobin (Gm%)	10.0	11.2	10.1-16.1
Total R.B.C (X 10 ⁶ /cum)	4.6	5.3	6.0-10.4
Total Leucocyte count (X 10 ³ /cum)	23.2	10.8	5.6-12.1
Differential Leucocyte count			
Neutrophil (%)	84	64	52-70
Lymphocyte (%)	14	32	21-42
Eosinophil (%)	0		0-7
Monocyte (%)	2	2	0-6
Basophil (%)	0	2	0-2
Billirubin (%)	6.8	0.3	0-3.2
S.G.P.T (IU/L)	40	41	10-109
S.G.O.T (IU/L)	12	13	13-15
Blood urea Nitrogen (mg/dl)	25	24	11-27
Creatinine (mg/dl)	1.4	1.5	0.4-2.2

Fig 1. Colour change in mucous membrane: Before treatment- (conjunctival (a), buccal (c), after treatment- (conjunctiva (b), buccal (d))

Fig 2: Latex agglutination test for *Leptospira* sp.

Fig 3: Microscopic Agglutination Test, a) control, b) *L. icterohemorrhagica* Pomona (1:100)

Fig 4: Gradual change of urine color during treatment

10 ml IM OD, Inj. Vitamin B-complex (Conciplex) ® @ 10 ml IM OD, Syrup. Brotone @ 50 ml orally OD along with fluid therapy for five days. After five days of treatment, the horse was clinically recovered uneventfully. Icteric mucous membrane returned to normal

Discussion

Clinical equine leptospirosis is characterized by recurrent uveitis, abortions, stillbirth, neonatal disease, hemolysis, renal disease, and liver disease (Broux et al., 2012). Serological testing is the most widely used method for diagnosing leptospirosis (Verma et al., 2013). Treatment of acute leptospirosis in individual animals is dependent on the use of antibiotics and supportive symptomatic treatment. Fluid therapy is almost always indicated to avoid hemoglobinuric nephrosis. In acute cases, systemic antibiotics such as enrofloxacin, penicillin, tetracycline, or aminoglycosides are useful (Aiello and Moses, 2016). A combination of penicillin and streptomycin has been the choice of antibiotic therapy for the treatment of acute leptospirosis (Ellis, 2015). However, streptomycin usage in horses is limited due to severe toxic side effects (Bernard, 1993).

References

- Adler, B. and de la Peña Moctezuma, A. 2010. *Leptospira* and leptospirosis. *Veterinary Microbiology*, **140(3-4)**, pp.287-296.
- Aiello, SE. and Moses, MA. 2016. *The Merck Veterinary Manual*. Kenilworth: Merck & Co.
- Bernard, W.V. 1993. Leptospirosis. *Vet. Clin. North Am. Equine Pract.* **9**, 435-444
- Bharti, A.R., Nally, J.E., Ricaldi, J.N., Matthias, M.A., Diaz, M.M., Lovett, M.A., Levett, P., Gilman, R.H., Willig, M.R., Gotuzzo, E. and Vinetz, J.M.. 2003. Leptospirosis: a zoonotic disease of global importance. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, **3(12)**, pp.757-771.
- Broux, B., Torfs, S., Wegge, B., Deprez, P. and Loon, GV, 2012. Acute respiratory failure caused by *Leptospira* spp. in 5 foals. *Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine*, **26(3)**, p.684.
- Ellis, W.A., 2015. Animal leptospirosis. In *Leptospira and leptospirosis* (pp. 99-137). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg
- Hathaway, S.C., Little, T.W., Finch, .M. and Stevens, A.E. 1981. Leptospiral infection in horses in England: a serological study. *Veterinary Record*, **108(18)**, pp.396-398.
- Levett, P.N. 2001. Leptospirosis. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* **14**, 296-32
- Verma, A., Stevenson, B. and Adler, B. 2013. Leptospirosis in horses. *Veterinary Microbiology*, **167(1-2)**, pp.61-66.
- Vinetz, J. 1997. Leptospirosis. *Curr. Opin. Infect. Dis.* **10**, 357361
- Wood, J.L.N., Townsend H.G.G. 1999. Leptospiral infections associated with disease and fertility in horses. *J. Anim. Breed.* **3**, 39-45

Received : 16.12.2019

Accepted : 21.06.2020